

AUGMENTED REALITY FOR PILOT TRAINING IN FLIGHT SIMULATORS*

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Introduction

Virtual Reality (VR) is the system that allows user to immerse into the virtual world. In contrary, Augmented Reality (AR) (e.g. the review of Arena et al. [1]) is the technology which merges the real and virtual world into one whole. It is realized by diffractive head-up glasses or smartphones. In both cases the user can see the real world and additional virtual objects combined with the reality, called *holograms*. There are also possible interactions between holograms and user or between holograms and the real world object.

On the other hand, the training of pilots in flight simulators is limited non only because of the equipment availability, but also due to the occupancy of the flight trainers. Moesl et al. in [2] shows that there are some procedures that are much more difficult to train than others, like (ibidem, Fig. 1): missed approach, landings, flight management system, take-offs, etc. Based on the references of pilots as well as instructors, the usefulness of AR devices for pilot training (ibidem, Fig. 3), especially in the area of aircraft structure and equipment, emergency procedures and flight preparation (which are most beneficial from the perspective of flight trainers) is indicated. Nevertheless, they've suggested the benefit level of AR application in much more types of procedures. Arjoni et al. in [3] focuses on the simulation of the “following the leader” case, which is implemented in two variants: levelled and curved flight. They compare different types of augmentation including wearing AR glasses. They proved experimentally that the introduction of augmented reality to pilot training improves the effectiveness and final quality of training (ibidem, pp. 9-16, sec. Results).

In this paper, we present the prototype of the novel system of AR-aided pilot training in flight simulators. The pilot training task can be realized with or without trainer assistance.

Overview & Implementation

Figure 3. The screenshot of VRM pilot training system. On the left picture there is shown defining flight procedure by admin, on the middle one, the realization of the “aircraft structure and equipment” training. On the right one – the localization and QR recognition for calibration of the system.

After the system is launched, it has to be calibrated. This process lies on two algorithms: SLAM (Simultaneous Localization and Mapping) and 3D-surface reconstruction (see Sheng et al. [4]) already implemented on

Figure 4. The use-case diagram of the system

HoloLens 2 device, which we use in the system. With this algorithm, we exploited the QR code detection and recognition, described by Skurowski et al. in [5], for determining the first pose of the headset in the simulator environment that was reconstructed by SLAM. The reconstructed mesh and the QR code recognition are shown in Figure 3 (the most right picture). The mesh can be seen as the bluish set of triangles, which covers the whole cockpit however, for convenience reasons, it is not drawn in the middle of the view. Figure 3 presented also the QR code located in the simulator, that we use for the first pose determination. The functionalities of the system are shown in Figure 4. **The training program** starts with the user's choice of procedure. Then, the chosen procedure can be executed in training and evaluation mode. In training mode, the user is guided by a system. It is done by a set of menu elements, like illumination (virtual) of the parts of the cockpit, that the trainee should pay attention to. The system of pointers shows the direction where the next interested area is placed, etc. Users can pause the simulation at any arbitrarily chosen point and see the procedure documentation. In the evaluation mode, there are no hints and the examined pilot has to go through the whole procedure on her/his own. The exemplary user action is shown in Figure 1 (middle picture). There is a speed brake tagged by a blue cube and the question: "Are the speed brake armed?". The user can answer: "Yes" or "No".

The administration module allows for the establishment of the relation between the recognized elements of the surroundings (in the case of the flight simulator - cockpit), and the concrete command/action in the training procedure, see Figure 1 (leftmost picture). Administrator can put the holographs being a tagging area around the selected surroundings elements, add information as well as references to procedure documentation and finally, the questions and proper answers.

The detection and recognition of the flight simulator's complexity depend on the elements that are in the area of interest. Some of them are relatively easy for the detection and recognition, like shuttlecock, levers, chairs, etc. However in the context of determining the clocks, indicators or especially small switches arranged in large blocks, we must say that proper recognition of them is practically impossible (e.g., Nurzyńska et al. [6]). Therefore, we decided to use a semi-automated system, where there are preliminary detected elements that have to be adjusted by the instructor at the level of scenario definition. Similarly, it is not possible to recognize the position of switches. Luckily, that information can be obtained from the simulator, therefore the AR system is integrated with the whole flight simulator through API.

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